

Brief information about treatment and self-management

If you have diabetes, you have to make sure that there is not too much or too little glucose in your blood. To do this, you need to take tablets or injections if the doctor prescribed them. You need to exercise regularly, eat small and regular healthy meals. Regular exercises and healthy eating will help you lose weight. You do not smoke. You limit your alcohol drinking. Have regular blood tests for glucose as prescribed by the doctor.